

Analysis of the competitiveness of cocoa producers in the south region of Tacotalpa, Tabasco

Gonzalo Gutiérrez Jiménez, Zenaida Guerra Que, José Luis Madrigal Eliseo, Javier Cruz Pérez, Casandra Ángeles Guzmán

National Technological Institute of Mexico / Technological Institute of Villahermosa / Graduate Studies Division

Abstract

The present research aims to analyze the competitiveness of cacao producers in the southern region of Tacotalpa, Tabasco, one of the state's main productive activities. Through interviews, field observations, and literature review, the research identified that the main factors affecting competitiveness are social, cultural, technical, and technological in nature. Specifically, fear of change, resistance to training, and a weak culture of organization were found to be significant barriers limiting technological adoption and access to differentiated markets. This interaction between social and technical factors creates a vicious cycle that deepens the sector's vulnerability.

Finally, it is concluded that strengthening the competitiveness of the cacao sector in Tacotalpa requires a profound transformation in rural education, merit-based culture, and collective organization. Advancing toward a model that promotes real market-oriented capabilities, collaborative leadership, and long-term vision is essential for producers to successfully integrate into international market demands, while maintaining the social and cultural balance that defines Tabasco's rural communities.

Resumen

La presente investigación tiene como finalidad analizar la competitividad de los productores de cacao en la región sur de Tacotalpa, Tabasco, una actividad que constituye una de las principales vocaciones productivas del estado. A través de entrevistas, observaciones de campo y revisión bibliográfica, se identificó que los principales factores que afectan la competitividad son de naturaleza social, cultural, técnica y tecnológica. En particular, se evidenció que el miedo al cambio, la resistencia a la capacitación y la escasa cultura organizativa actúan como barreras significativas, limitando la adopción de tecnologías y el acceso a mercados diferenciados. Esta interacción entre factores sociales y técnicos genera un círculo vicioso que profundiza la vulnerabilidad del sector.

Finalmente, se concluye que el fortalecimiento de la competitividad del sector cacaotero en Tacotalpa no puede lograrse sin una transformación profunda en la educación rural, la cultura del mérito y la organización colectiva. Se propone avanzar hacia un modelo que promueva el desarrollo de capacidades reales orientadas al mercado, el liderazgo colaborativo y una visión de largo plazo, como condición necesaria para que los productores puedan insertarse con éxito en las exigencias de los mercados internacionales, sin perder el equilibrio social ni cultural que caracteriza a las comunidades rurales de Tabasco.

Keywords: Competitiveness, Cocoa, Factors

Palabras Clave: Competitividad, Cacao, Factores

1. INTRODUCTION

Classical economic theories laid the foundations of the concept of competitiveness, focusing their analysis on economic factors such as production costs, comparative advantages, and market conditions (Rojas & Sepúlveda G., 1999). However, in recent decades, business dynamics and economic environments have evolved, incorporating new elements into the competitiveness analysis. Currently, factors such as technological innovation, continuous organizational improvements, and the capacity to adapt to change are considered essential for the sustainable development of products and services.

In this context, agriculture remains one of Mexico's main economic activities. The state of Tabasco stands out for its high cocoa production, contributing approximately 70% of the national total (SIAP, 2024). Traditionally, the Chontalpa region has led this production with consolidated organizational systems and advanced competitive practices.

However, regions like the south of Tacotalpa have begun experiencing growth in cocoa production but face significant challenges in terms of grain quality standardization, commercialization, and organizational culture. This reality highlights the need for a comprehensive analysis that considers productive, commercial, organizational, and socioeconomic factors affecting the competitiveness of local producers, with the aim of identifying opportunities and designing strategies to strengthen the cocoa sector.

In this sense, the present research proposes to analyze the factors affecting the competitiveness of cocoa producers in the south region of Tacotalpa, Tabasco, through a systemic approach that includes political, economic, social, cultural, technical, and environmental variables. From this diagnosis, the goal is to formulate a proposal aimed at improving productivity, collective organization, and market access, thus contributing to the sustainable and equitable development of cocoa-growing communities in the region.

Competitiveness

Over time, classical economic theories shaped the definition of competitiveness, originally more closely tied to economics; however, economic terms and conditions change, leading to new circumstances that require adaptation to the new market.

According to Rojas & Sepúlveda (1999), “There are words that have the gift of being exceptionally precise, specific, and at the same time, extremely generic, unlimited; highly operational and measurable, and yet considerably abstract and extensive. However, whatever the case, these words have the privilege of shaping behaviors and perspectives, as well as, resembling more to evaluation tools, exert influence in practical life. One of these magic words is ‘competitiveness’.”

Problems in the Decline of Cocoa Competitiveness in Mexico

The competitiveness of cocoa in Mexico, especially in Tabasco, has faced a series of problems that have caused a significant decline in production. These problems can be grouped into climatic, agronomic, socioeconomic, and institutional support factors.

Social Factor

Social factors play a crucial role in the competitiveness of companies and economic sectors. According to CEPAL (2022), Jenzano (2016), and the International Labour Organization (2019), the social dimension is fundamental to understanding the capacity of rural cocoa producers to participate effectively and sustainably in markets. Factors such as community organization, access to education, gender equity, and migration directly or indirectly influence their productivity, innovation, and sustainability.

Economic Factors

Economic factors are key elements influencing the competitiveness of companies and sectors in a market. According to FAO (2021), the economic competitiveness of cocoa producers depends on their ability to produce

at low cost, maintain good quality, access markets, and adapt to changing conditions. The economic factors impacting this process are diverse and can represent both barriers and opportunities.

Political Factors

Political factors are key elements that can significantly influence the competitiveness of companies and economic sectors. El-Hage Scialabba & Hattam (2003), mention that the competitiveness of rural cocoa producers depends not only on technical or economic factors but also on a stable, fair, and favorable political environment. Public policies, local governance, and relations with the State directly impact access to resources, legal security, and development opportunities for the sector.

Technical Factors

Technical factors are crucial elements influencing the competitiveness of companies, such as pests, lack of technological tools, and their proper use, especially in an increasingly globalized and technological environment (Evans C et al., 2018), (Aime C & Mora Phillips, 2005).

Environmental Factors

Environmental factors can influence the competitiveness of companies, particularly in a context where sustainability and social responsibility are increasingly relevant. The FAO Climate Change Strategy 2022–2031 (2024), notes that cocoa production directly depends on environmental conditions such as climate, biodiversity, soil quality, and water availability. Rural producers, especially small-scale ones, face growing challenges due to climate change, environmental degradation, and pressure on natural resources.

Cultural Factors

Hernández Gómez et al., (2005), mention that local culture directly influences agricultural practices, social organization, work perception, and the approach to cocoa commercialization. Recognizing and valuing cultural factors allows strengthening competitiveness through a more inclusive, sustainable, and authentic development model (Portillo & Portillo, 2012).

2. METHODOLOGY

To analyze the economic, cultural, political, technical, social, and environmental factors affecting competitiveness in the cocoa sector in the south of Tacotalpa, Tabasco, a diagnosis and evaluation of variables were conducted through theoretical saturation-based sampling, recording information in tables that gathered data from the area. This methodology was applied in communities covering the south of Tacotalpa.

Trinidad Requena et al., (2006), mention that theoretical saturation sampling is a common approach in qualitative studies that consists of selecting participants until the data reach a saturation point, i.e., when no new ideas, concepts, or categories emerge. This type of sampling focuses more on data richness than sample quantity. Theoretical saturation is reached when additional information does not significantly advance the understanding of the variables or phenomena under study. Instead of random sampling, the researcher intentionally chooses participants who can provide deep and detailed information, facilitating the development of emerging theories and providing a more comprehensive understanding of the investigated phenomenon.

To achieve this, the following information collection and analysis strategies were focused on.

Figure 1. Diagram of the applied methodology

3. RESULTS

To better understand competitiveness in the south of Tacotalpa, Tabasco, the general information from the instrument is presented below, represented in graphs with a significance percentage for the general responses to each question applied.

A total of 20 surveys were conducted in different communities, as theoretical saturation analysis showed that conducting more surveys was unnecessary due to repetitive responses that did not add new data to the research.

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Cocoa production in the study region is a practice preserved to this day, with the difference that it has grown in recent years. The cultivation is an inheritance for people who remain with their parents' land, although currently social programs like “Sembrando Vida” have been increasing cocoa production in communities, opening market opportunities in the region.

Based on the instrument, the information obtained was captured and analyzed using Excel.

The elements affecting competitiveness were classified as follows:

- Training and Technical knowledge
- Infrastructure and logistics
- Organization and collaboration
- Adoption of new technologies
- Market and commercialization
- Climatic conditions
- Institutional support
- Social factors

Table 1. Results based on training and technical knowledge.

Training and Technical Knowledge

Based on the results obtained from the chart regarding training and technical knowledge, it is evident that there are challenges within the working groups. One hundred percent (100%) of the respondents indicated that effective communication is difficult to achieve, as certain issues tend to escalate, which in turn delays decision-making processes, as well as the planning of work activities and group tasks.

Regarding the use of traditional techniques in plantations, 90% of respondents stated that they continue to apply the methods they learned from their parents. This often leads to delays in field activities and, in some cases, to the underutilization of organic products that are available to them. Conversely, 10% reported that they do not experience difficulties in this regard. For example, in crop maintenance, some producers use mechanical trimmers, significantly reducing the time required to complete the task—by more than half—compared to using machetes. The time required also increases depending on the size of the plantation. One producer stated: “When I carry out cleaning, it takes me a long time, even when two of us are working. By the time we reach the end, the area where we started has already begun to grow again because my plantation is large.”

On the other hand, 100% of the producers mentioned that governance does exist within their working groups and that it is a deeply rooted practice. Decision-making is carried out through consensus, with members expressing their opinions, and once an agreement is reached, formal minutes are prepared and signed by all participants.

Table 2. Results based on infrastructure and logistics in the region

On the other hand, regarding infrastructure and logistics, respondents indicated that there are indeed infrastructure-related challenges, with 100% of producers stating that although they do have a designated workspace, it requires improvements. In many cases, work areas need to be properly adapted, as the available space may be limited or, in some instances, deteriorated, given that most of the structures are primarily made of wood.

With respect to logistics, 50% of the producers reported facing logistical challenges, while the remaining 50% indicated that they do not. Some producers choose to sell to four companies or buyers who enter the communities on a weekly basis to purchase cocoa. The other half typically sells at a government-designated strategic location where better prices are offered; however, this site is somewhat distant for producers in the region, resulting in additional time and logistical expenses to transport their product. Furthermore, regarding logistics, half of the respondents reported having access to harvest roads and therefore do not encounter significant difficulties in transporting their product from the farm to their homes, while the other half does face such challenges and often requires more time to move their product.

Finally, 100% of the producers reported difficulties with proper storage, as they do not have a specific designated facility. Instead, they seek suitable spaces within their homes where there is no humidity to store the cocoa, particularly when preparing it for sale in its dried form.

Table 3. Results based on organization and collaboration

Organization and Collaboration

Regarding the elements of organization and collaboration, 100% of the respondents mentioned that they have weaknesses in the cooperative since they have not yet found that harmony of group work and mutual support. On the other hand, 100% of the respondents indicated organizational weaknesses—not so much in agreements, but when carrying out group activities, they enter into debates about tasks, do not have an activity program, experience slow decision-making, limitations in producers taking initiative, and a lack of attitude and aptitude.

Finally, 55% of the producers do not belong to a formal cooperative; however, they are part of the "Sembrando Vida" program. It is worth mentioning that they do have a work structure but do not carry it out as it should be. Meanwhile, 45% do belong to a formal cooperative and are working on it, meaning they still have difficulties in how to work within a cooperative society, but these are the people who said that it must be formal because they see it as a good business.

Table 4. Results based on the adoption of new technologies

Adoption of new technologies

Regarding the adoption of new technologies, the findings indicate that 90% of respondents are unfamiliar with the use of equipment and tools in the field, as they carry out their activities in the manner taught by their parents or according to common regional practices. Likewise, the municipality of Tacotalpa is not widely recognized as a major cocoa-producing area, and as a result, technological innovations implemented in other regions are not well known locally. Meanwhile, 10% of respondents stated that they are familiar with the subject and use at least one tool in the field, particularly for maintaining the cleanliness of their plantations.

Furthermore, 95% of those interviewed believe that adopting new technologies requires a high level of investment, as they lack sufficient financial resources to invest significantly in their plantations. The remaining 5% indicated that, although the initial investment may be costly, it ultimately results in savings of both time and money compared to traditional methods.

Table 5. Results based on market and commercialization

Regarding the market and commercialization elements, 100% of the producers reported that there is no weak bargaining position, as there is a stable market for cocoa and they are satisfied with the prices at which they sell their product. While 10% indicated a lack of access to markets, 90% stated that this is not an issue.

According to the respondents, a sufficient market exists because a few companies enter the communities to purchase all the cocoa produced in the region.

Furthermore, 5% mentioned that intermediaries are present in the region; however, 95% indicated that there are none, as certain companies maintain direct contact within the communities. The presence of intermediaries occurs only after the harvest season has concluded.

Table 6. Results obtained on climatic and environmental conditions

Regarding climatic and environmental conditions, 100% of the respondents agreed that they are being affected by climate change, as the seasons have become unpredictable and temperatures have shifted compared to previous years.

Consequently, 95% reported being affected by pests and diseases, with *Moniliophthora* (moniliasis) being the most significant concern.

Table 7. Results obtained on institutional support and public policies

Regarding institutional support and public policies, 100% of respondents agreed that social programs and support are present in the region. However, 70% indicated that more follow-up is needed, as in some cases these programs are not properly managed. They explained: “The technicians who collect information enforce the program’s requirements, but there are conflicts with producers who do not have their plants or make no effort to replant them. Those who comply often express dissatisfaction because they are charged for the non-

compliant producers, and the technician only explains that removals follow a process and cannot be immediately canceled or suspended. Similarly, some working groups show little interest in the program and execute tasks partially; without proper follow-up, the program’s objectives are not fully achieved.” The remaining 30% stated that no additional follow-up is necessary for the social programs.

Regarding delayed or poorly managed support, 30% of respondents acknowledged that some programs are mismanaged or consistently have the same issues. Conversely, 70% responded negatively, emphasizing that support is generally timely and beneficial as long as it reaches the farmers and is effectively applied to all rural community members, providing real advantages.

Finally, 100% of respondents reported that they do not have an independent source of financing and rely entirely on their own income and the assistance provided by the program.

Table 8. Results obtained on social factors

Finally, regarding social factors, 75% of respondents indicated that there is a prevailing sense of distrust within the organization, as they are not accustomed to working in teams. This sometimes creates difficulties in communicating effectively within work groups, which can foster distrust, influenced in large part by each individual’s work culture. The remaining 25% stated that they do not experience difficulties interacting with others, provided there is a collaborative work synergy.

Additionally, 50% of respondents reported a lack of motivation, while the other 50% indicated that this is not an issue. Several factors influence these responses, including limited knowledge of the cocoa market, the advanced age of some producers with fixed mindsets, and challenges in managing their plantations. This also impacts the following aspect: 50% of respondents have limited entrepreneurial vision, whereas the other 50% disagreed. The latter group is in a growth phase, participating in a collaborative program with a company that provides workshops aimed at improving cocoa quality and developing the skills needed to operate as a formal cooperative.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The competitiveness of cocoa producers in the south region of Tacotalpa, Tabasco, is conditioned by a complex interaction of social, cultural, technical, political, economic, and environmental factors. The study shows that despite significant potential for cocoa cultivation, lack of effective organization, resistance to technological change, infrastructure limitations, and poor institutional support hinder sector development. Traditional practices and low innovation adoption obstruct competitiveness and product quality improvements, while insufficient training and low social cohesion limit producers' capacity to enter more competitive, higher-value markets.

Adverse climatic conditions and diseases like moniliasis present significant challenges impacting yields and sustainability. Implementing an integral model fostering inclusive training, strengthening collective organization, participative leadership, and adopting appropriate technologies is essential to elevate sector competitiveness. This model should also incorporate environmental and cultural perspectives respecting and enhancing local traditions, ensuring sustainable and equitable development.

Finally, progress toward a more competitive production and commercialization system requires coordinated commitment among producers, government institutions, and private actors to overcome existing barriers and seize national and international market opportunities. Only through profound transformation in rural education, merit culture, and collective management can Tacotalpa's cocoa producers consolidate market position, increase income, and contribute to regional economic and social development.

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Correo de autor de correspondencia: m23301193@villahermosa.tecnm.mx, gonzalogutierrezjimenez33@gmail.com